

Utilizing Smart Energy Networks to Mitigate Smart Seaport Carbon Footprint

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Abstract

The European Maritime Spatial Planning Platform issued “Green airports and ports as multimodal hubs for sustainable and intelligent mobility program, “then all ports shall demonstrate integrated low-emission energy supply and production at ports and supply systems, with storage, distribution, and sustainable alternative fuel refueling infrastructure for ships and other vehicles operating at/to/from ports, as well as for other uses. On the other hand, the smart seaport is “a port in which all operations, including terminal, warehousing, logistics, yard, and port transportation, are closely connected through the wireless network or special network, providing all kinds of information for daily operations.”. Furthermore, an essential component of a smart port is intelligent management to control and manage all port operations and balance energy demand and supply intelligently by using intelligent tools like the internet of things and intelligent grids.

Then, seaports need to minimize internal port boundary’s energy consumption or replace them with renewable energies according to international guidelines such as ISO 50001 and Port Energy Management Plans.

This research surveys the carbon footprint reduction caused by fuel consumption reduction, which results from using smart energy networks in electricity production, distribution, and consumption.

Keywords: smart seaport, carbon footprint, energy management, internet of things, intelligent grids.

1. Introduction

In technological settings, smart refers to automated computational principles such as self-configuration, self-protection, self-healing, and self-optimization [6]. In urban planning, smart growth emerged during the 1990s as a state of course and focus in response to the increasing trend of destruction of people's living environment, noise, air pollution, destruction of historical sites, traffic congestion, and the increase in the cost of public facilities.[7]

The term "smart growth" refers to a prospective (public or private) to managing developments that leads to managerial, economic, and environmental improvements Progress without congestion and environmental degradation [8]. A smart city maximizes services to citizens while Monitoring and integrating critical infrastructure, planning preventive maintenance measures, optimizing resources, and increasing security aspects' monitoring.[9]

The word smart seaport also is gained from the smart city by the same concept but with a smaller scale and distinguished missions: sustainability and profit. Each of them can be interpretative in several issues [10]. One of the main objectives of sustainability is about energy issues and new systems and initiatives in energy generation, distribution, and consumption. An energy management system (EMS) is a new system in this field commonly used in all smart seaports [11]. Conversely, there is a substantial proportion between the energy management system and carbon footprint (C.F) reduction. Smart port authorities, like other industrial sites, have started to perform new initiatives in the mentioned issue to use intelligent management with intelligent infrastructures and equipment to mitigate carbon emissions and reduce the C.F in maritime ports [12]. This study will illustrate and modify the C.F mitigation in smart maritime ports aligned with the SDGs by managing energy production, distribution, and consumption via a smart grid system. Then the results are to be discussed in a literature review manner.

2. Methodology

This research is a cross-sectional descriptive literature review of related resources, including articles, eBooks, official websites, etc., concerning mitigating C.F in smart ports using smart energy networks. Due to the novelty of this topic and the characteristics of C.F and intelligent ports, the issue of sustainability is one of the most important criteria for an intelligent energy network. It has a solid connection with climate change, showing the importance of mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and systematically reducing industrial sites like seaports; these procedures need innovative webs and girds. These intelligent grid operations use databases, and data analysis, intelligent management, and these procedures fit into the same theme of smart ports .

Following a well-documented guide for developing PRISMA literature review protocols, the critical literature review was conducted in 5 main steps: (i) online database search based on keywords and selection criteria; (ii)refining as per criteria such as language, document type, year, (iii) further refinement based on keywords; (iv) abstract screening; and (v) full-text review. This systematic process is outlined in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Methodology.

3. Literature review

Borrowing the philosophy of choosing the word from the field of smart city, it can be said that the digital port describes. We know that the word smart is different from the word digital. An intelligent set is thanks to several digital departments connected with digital infrastructure and intelligent management. Through effective communication, the connection port combines broadband communication, infrastructure, flexible and service-oriented computing infrastructure, and fast and innovative services to meet demands. A smart port has all the infrastructure and information structure, information technology, and the latest telecommunications, electronics, and mechanics technologies. A knowledge port is designed to encourage knowledge cultivation. A human harbor has many opportunities to use Its human potential and direction of creative processes3] . A smart port has intelligent management, intelligent transportation, intelligent economy, intelligent healthcare system, intelligent energy, intelligent communication, intelligent grid, intelligent buildings, better-educated people, skilled workforces, intelligent infrastructure, and automation to facilitate knowledge development. Furthermore, optimizing port operations and increasing port resilience leads to stable and guaranteed development and Safe and secure port activities[3] . Also, a smart port has three main components that can be subcategorized into different sub-components: intelligent infrastructure, intelligent traffic fellow, and intelligent logistics [10]. as shown in figure 2;

Figure 2. Key Component of Smart Seaport.

On the other hand, each smart port has a scope of activities that can be classified as follows: I) operation and ii) environment. iii)energy, iv) safety, and v) security [8]. However, each of them can be categorized as smaller branches too.

The operation can categorize as follows: A) productivity: it can be illustrated as balancing demands and supplying primary port services, including loading/ unloading cargo, shifting cargo inside the port territory, managing traffic density inside ports, port clearance operation, etc. (Smart Port, n.d.). B) Automation can be defined as utilizing different methods of using machinery instead of human force, but with their supervision, it can increase service efficacy and save time [13]. C) intelligent infrastructure: it means utilizing intelligent departments of a smart port which can collaborate in an intelligent form using intelligent communication and IoT [1].

The environment can be classified as follows: A) environmental management system: any activity that can help ports activities goal to align with the protecting environment management can be illustrated in this domain [3]. B) emission and pollution control: all activities to control and mitigate emissions inside port territories governed by port authorities or public authority according to the national and international regulations can be illustrated as control initiatives in ports [6]. C) waste and water management: include all activities for balancing demand and supply for water management as a vital substance in the world and then moves for controlling and receiving waste materials and then using them in case of possibility for other industries like renewable energies, etc. [14].

Energy can be categorized as A) efficient energy consumption: many guidelines and international and national regulations concern efficient energy use of ships, vehicles, equipment and buildings, factories, and generators inside ports that all of them are aligned to reach efficient energy consumption in seaports. [15]. B) Renewable energies and their production: the second action and minimizing fossil energy use is to produce renewable energies like wind energy, solar energy, earth thermal energy, and sea energy, then prepare for use inside seaports, and it can be one of the main objectives of smart seaport authorities and policymakers. [16]. C) energy management: all activities and functions by the port authorities to issue main port strategies for efficient energy use and activities around this issue [3].

Safety: all activity to maintain port safety in public and private operations must be monitored and supervised according to the standard guidelines in smart seaports by using intelligent facilities.[12]

Security: all initiatives, operations, and activities for seaport security need to use intelligent infrastructure alongside technologies and monitoring; these procedures are defined as security activities of a smart port [17].[18] [

As mentioned in the last parts, each smart port has components that collaborate in an intelligent form and wise policy; an intelligent management system leads this form and guidelines [12]. The smart port management system needs intelligence in vessel traffic, cargo handling, port management, energy, and resources [12]. Figure 3 shows critical sectors of a smart port management system.

Figure 3 . Smart Seaport Management Sections.

A) Intelligent vessel management can make vessels traffic management (VTS) and vessel traffic management services (VTMS), and other navigational services for all vessels in the port territory.

B) intelligent cargo handling management system, including all loading, discharging, shifting, and striping warehousing in/from a smart port which can be delivered intelligently and using intelligent infrastructures and equipment.

C) intelligent port management includes all decisions and policies and their application system in an innovative method and by utilizing intelligent systems of automation.

D) intelligent energy management consists of all activities to balance energy supply and demand inside the port, regulate efficient energy use, and attempt to replace renewable and green energies instead of fossil fuels.

E) intelligent resource management schedules and allocates resources, including equipment and infrastructures, to reduce congestion and identify the sources of congestion to optimize resource procurement and allocation in terms of time and cost. This helps to reduce resource wastage and waiting and inactivity time [12].

The main issue for this research is surveying in Smart Energy Networks, which can generally be divided into three critical scopes: A) power generation (energy supply). B) energy distribution, C) energy consumption (energy demand), and D) moving toward renewable energies and replacing them instead of fossil fuel energies [3], which will be discussed later.

4. Result and Discussion

4-1- Energy Management System

The recent prospective of information and communication technology (ICT) applications for fabrications, constructions, and building automation networks has raised the feasibility of utilizing intelligent energy systems in building and commercial constructions. This issue is focused on the awareness of the environmental impacts of energy generation and consumption [19]. The world's energy need is anticipated to grow in the following decades due to population increase and industrial potential. The industry section outlined to raise its energy demand by 40% by 2040 [20]. Global energy necessities forecast indicates a vital need for efficient strategies to mitigate energy use, and an Environmental Impact Energy Management System (EMS) is a capability that can minimize energy consumption in fabrications and industries via various effective strategies [21]. Increasing energy prices and decreasing resources improved

energy management in the 1970s [22]. EMS's main issue is optimizing energy prices without lowering their impact or quality while mitigating environmental effects [23]. The contemporary perspective of energy management systems for maritime ports outlines intelligent, effective, safe, and affordable solutions.

This system applies to 3 issues: energy generation, energy consumption, and renewable energy production. Energy generation refers to activities in the port that convert energy into electricity. Energy use refers to using electricity for port and port-related activities, such as cargo handling and industrial processes, logistics, and administrative activities [3]. Nowadays, energy is generated mainly through using fossil fuel resources in main ports but managing to optimize its consumption is one of the critical issues that are concern by authorities worldwide. Also, Energy use can be classified into.[3]

A) Energy required for direct port activities, such as terminals, locks and bridges, administration buildings, buoys, and lighting.

B) Energy required for powering ships (fuel consumed and electricity provided to ships.)

C)Energy required for port-related and port-induced activities, such as refineries, railway operations, steel and metal works, and tourism.

Renewable energy plays an essential role within ports, as they are often located in areas particularly suitable for power generation from wind (e.g., Rotterdam, Kitakyushu in Japan) and waves.

(e.g., Port Kembla in Australia or Mutriku in the Basque Country), tide differentials (under study, for example, in Dover, UK, and the Port of Digby, Nova Scotia), and in some cases, geothermal energy (see the Hamburg case). Furthermore, ports often have broad flat surfaces available, such as storage areas and warehouses, that can be used to install solar panels (e.g., the Tokyo Ohi Terminal or the Port of San Diego administration buildings). However, such infrastructure might only sometimes suit large-scale solar energy exploitation. The development of the renewable

The energy sector also impacts ports through project cargo for offshore renewable energy installations and support services for wind farms.[3]

Although managing energy in seaports needs management tools: policies, and Technological and Operational Measures, as follows :[5]

Policy side: policies and guidelines for EMS in maritime ports can be national and international, and both focus on optimizing EMS goals. Still, some of the leading international policies can be enumerated as follows:

- ISO 50001 'Energy Management.
- EN 16001 'Energy Management Systems.
- Port Energy Management Plans (PeMP).
- Energy Management Addressed via Environmental Management Systems (EMS).
- Port Environmental Management Plans (PEMP) and Green Port Policies.

Technological and Operational Measures Adopted for Improving Energy Efficiency:

- Categorization of activities inside the port (direct and indirect or land-based and maritime-based).

- Key operational measures.
- Main Technological Solutions for Port/Terminal Equipment and Vehicles.
- Energy-Efficient Port Buildings.
- Other Infrastructure and Facilities Supporting Port Energy Efficiency.

This recent EMS is part of the Distributed Energy Resources initiative. Energy-producing services that are directly linked to medium voltage (MV) or low voltage (LV) delivery grids are outlined as distributed energy resources (DER) rather than bulk energy broadcasting systems [23]. The new perspective that manages energy use through DERs consists of the intelligent grid, microgrid, and virtual power plant, which are discussed in more depth in the following section. Figure 4 illustrates parts of DER in the energy management system.

Figure 4 . parts of the Distribution of Energy Resources in the Energy Management System.

4-2- Virtual Power Plant

Due to the rising penetration of distributed generation units and their capability to exchange energy produced from conventional power plants, high technology is required to meet the electricity requirements of consumers from an affordable and safe aspect [24]. The growth deployment of Distributed generation (DG) and the shortage of a passive perspective demonstrate long-term investing in DG governance. There is an urgent need to adopt an effective system contributing to DG's participation in the energy business [25]. Although a virtual power plant (VPP) is defined as “a unique power plant that uses information and communication technology to link, monitor and visualize distributed generators (ICT)” [26]. A VPP virtual power plant can manage the power flow between various units. It can contribute to optimizing energy use and increase the efficiency of the systems [27]. Management and control, distribution and optimization, and integration of DG and renewable energy sources are the three vital functions of VPPs [28]. According to Refs, the purpose of VPP is to transfer energy with the grid web and monitor and control the supply flow and demand between users [29].

4-3- Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is dramatically employed for environmental modeling due to the acknowledgment of the potential of artificial intelligence to solve complex issues [30]. Artificial intelligence techniques utilize, optimize, simulate, control, supervise and monitor multi-complex systems such as intelligent control, timing, optimization, and complex mapping [30]. In the energy market, AI is critical in every section of the energy supply chain (from energy production to transmission via network and distribution to the final user) [31]. Artificial

intelligence can expand the energy performance of the systems via intelligent energy management systems for maritime ports [32]. Artificial Intelligence can also support power supply reliability and, at the same time, reduce electricity costs [33].

4-4- Information and Communication Technology

It is one of the essential factors in modern society. ICT also has a vital role in the industry. As defined by UNESCO, information and communication technology is “a combination of information technology and other related technologies, especially communication technology” [34]. In an intelligent grid, ICT is essential to establish a practical, flexible, and safe communication infrastructure and allow protocols to support real-time interactions between producers and users [35]. The most frequently used communication strategy is an intelligent meter and a data cloud via power line communication (PLC). The second perspective is a fusion of a data cloud and a data meter management system. GPS or GPRS is the most commonly used system [35].

4-5- Internet of Things

The Internet of Things (IoT) is an entirely new information technology subject with various applications and suggestions in industrial sections. The Internet is a worldwide system that links computer networks-based systems on a set of standard Internet protocols that perform vast numbers of users globally. Since the Internet is a grid of networks, including enormous numbers of private, public, educational, industrial, national, and international networks, industries such as maritime and ecosystems gain profits from Internet methods by performing different amounts of electronic network technologies.[36]

IoT helps to permit the secure and safe exchange of operational data between non-visible, embedded, and unique, recognizable devices through radio frequency identification (RFID) and wireless sensor networks (WSN) utilizing sensor devices and several processors to optimize the decision-making process to support automation [36]. Using IoT for maritime port operations is stated by Sarabia-Jacome, who improved a marine port data cloud that prevents stakeholder information system interoperability[37].

The results argued that the maritime port data clouds improve several port departments' decisions. Another research looking to use an automatic mooring system (AMS), which permits ships to berth and unberth without using their mooring machinery, found that it can mitigate carbon emissions [38].

4-6- Intelligence Network

Due to the direct current energy grid and restricted power voltage units, traditional energy-producing units supplied electricity to the nearest areas. Further renovations followed in the energy grid system, which supplied energy over long distances between energy units and buildings by utilizing technical instruments such as alternating current (AC) grids. This system is a decentralized power system [39]. Furthermore, they are improving the energy necessary to meet people's requirements for the following consumptions. The intelligent grid issue has

contributed to identifying high-quality, compatible production and storage units. The goal of an intelligent grid is to permit parties and policymakers to focus on determining a supreme operating environment for both electrical energy and consumers [40]. Raising the public perception of renewable and sustainable energy sources and, on the other hand, population increase and economic issues in modern and developing countries significantly impact the designing of electrical energy systems. This transition concentrates on intelligent, green, affordable, and anticible electrical system designs [41]. Intelligent grid technologies can collaborate to solve energy system problems to perform with reliable, safe, stable, and high-quality electricity. An intelligent grid has a positive impact because it permits renewable energy sources to connect with several city energy sources and increase the reliability and efficiency of the power system, as shown in Figure 5 [42]. It offers an intelligent grid at the smart seaport, a cargo terminal: (1) onshore power supply, (2) in-port crane and stowage equipment, (3) cargo handling cranes, and (4) buildings.

Figure 5. Intelligence Grid in Smart Seaport [42].

Consumers turn to active members of an intelligent grid utilizing energy systems to avert energy loss and mitigate energy use via a demand and response perspective. Also, Intelligent grids can profit more users by decreasing electricity energy costs and expanding incomes from energy sales during peak hours [43]. An intelligent grid uses digital technologies to grow the reliability, stability, and efficiency (both aspects of energy and economics) of the electrical system from an actual product, employing distribution links to electricity consumers and an enlarge the number of distributed products and storage origins, as per to the US Department of Energy [44]. Furthermore, intelligent grids depend on renewable energy origins such as sea energy, solar, thermal, and wind energy, which is fitful and undependable; that is one of the problems of increasing the outstretch of intelligent electric grids, particularly in maritime ports and industrial systems [43]. It can be identified via many technologies which go a long way to reach stability and pliability in electricity energy delivery, consisting of utilizing artificial intelligence to anticipate the amount of energy that will be generated in coming days and then store or convert it. Transform it into other forms of energy and then reutilize it and meet their requirements while users need it [45]. These criteria connect the intelligent grid to electricity

energy markets and profit consumers by lowering electricity energy costs and extending income from energy trading through peak hours [45].

4-7- Microgrid

Considering the increase of issues to restrict human-made greenhouse gas emissions, solutions shall be established for optimizing electrical energy and electricity production from fossil fuel resources. Likewise, according to the amplitude of the energy transition era, a study on microgrids made a fundamental suggestion for the future generation of electrical energy systems[46]. A microgrid is a compact local energy web that consists of loads, a grid control system, and a variety of distributed energy resources (DERs), together with energy producers and electricity storage systems. Microgrids are applied with intelligent elements For DERs need acknowledgment systems to communicate in delivery networks.[47]

According to the US Department of Energy, a microgrid is "a community of interconnected loads and distributed generation at defined electrical boundaries that rely on a controllable entity connected to the grid." A microgrid is grid-connected and disconnected, permitting it to run in a grid-connected or isolated method [48]. Microgrids in maritime ports include distributed energy resources (DER), energy exchanging equipment, communication links, control units, and energy management systems (EMS) that enable efficient energy management between parties and users[49]. Consequently, a microgrid is a fusion of renewable energy sources, electricity storage, control units, and users. It can also be a cross-generational system connected with grids [50]. Renewable energy sources (RES) lean on wind and tide, weather conditions, and Photovoltaic (PV) fragmentary resources [51]. On the other hand, system reliability shall be fixed, power needs to be predicted, and contingencies prevented for the efficient performance of a microgrid. Utilizing energy storage units for microgrids contributes to solving the unanticipated RES problem[52]. Microgrid performance, control, and collaboration are essential subjects influencing system performance [53]. Two studies employed optimization skills to mitigate errors and enlarge efficiency and profits for the system and its consumers [54] [55]. Figure 6 shows an overview of a microgrid system in a smart seaport. [56]

Figure 6. Microgrid System in Smart Seaport [56].

4-8- Distribution of Product

The past years have noticed a remarkable exchange in energy regulations and policies due to important subjects that could affect people's lives, such as the restriction amount of fossil resources and climate change, along with the severe growth rates in world population. Consequently, different countries have commenced using small energy generation systems to enlarge the security of providing and meeting energy demands.[57]

This system is identified as Distributed Generation (DG) or Decentralized Energy System (DES). DG must supply pliability and security to the grid by utilizing small energy plants and more competent generation.[58]

On the other hand, DG oppressed local energy generation resources and fixed energy storage units at local stations [59]. Important energy policies for DECs are let to decontrol the energy market and contribute to identifying climate change. This is projected in installing DECs and growing competition between organizations and parties [59]. Per a study by P. Paliwal and his team [60], the exchange from centralized to decentralized energy-producing is ongoing too rapidly. Furthermore, the assimilation of RES with decentralized energy systems may decrease trust in fossil fuels, enlarging power supply reliability and reducing C.F.

The issue of DG has many interpretations; the first one is expressed by T. Ackermann and his team, who defined DG from geographically based approaches as a “power source on the user side of the meter or inside distribution networks[61] ”.

Considering the research of L. Mehigan and his team, there are three DG classifications.:[62]

- A) distribution generations which are linked to the distribution network,
- B) distribution generators linked to the user’s side of the receiving device,
- C) distribution generators separate from the grid and depend on the energy demand.

DG consists of the traditional producing system and non-traditional producing one. Conventional generation: this system consists of devices such as microturbines. Figure 7 shows energy distribution in a smart maritime port with a multi-energy resource [63].

Figure 7. Seaport Multi Energy Distribution diagram [63].

Non-traditional producing methods include RES, storage devices (like batteries), and electrochemical equipment (fuel cells). There are various programs from DG. The DG can be kept in standby mode to provide the required energy at peak times or in urgent and vital situations. It can be utilized to produce electricity and supply high-performance combined heat and power at the regional level [64].

5. Conclusion

According to the results conducted in this research, there is a significant relationship between the energy management system and the amount of air pollution created worldwide. The effect of this relationship is more visible on large scales, such as industrial sites, because the performance of services and industrial productions, per capita energy consumption, is higher than the amount of activity and geographical area. One of the industrial and service sites can be seaports. The relationship between the energy management system and air pollution is inversely established in these areas, which means that the more efficient the energy management system is in a seaport, the more efficient the energy consumption is, the higher production and services performance and thus, If the amount of energy consumed on the scale of its service and production activity is reduced. This less energy consumption will emit fewer pollutants into the air; a considerable percentage (76%) of these pollutants are composed of carbon [65], so the creation of a management system Energy makes optimal use of energy, which will directly result in less air pollution and a lower C.F. In addition to mitigating C.F, this issue can significantly impact cost savings, affecting the industry's cost in local and international markets.

Figure 8 . Interrelation between Smart Network System and Mitigation Carbon Footprint.

Figure 8 shows the interrelation of EMS and a smart seaport to mitigate C.F. On the other hand, one of the components of smart ports is the establishment of intelligent infrastructures connected through the internet or intranet networks. By aligning the activities inside the port, it can be done due to intelligent and integrated systems and databases to avoid doing some activities again or in parallel. This will reduce unnecessary activities and consequently lessen the C.F. Nevertheless, by combining the meaning of smart ports and energy management system, we get an essential concept that the energy management system by using the infrastructure and components in the smart port, such as the Internet of Things, databases, artificial intelligent networks, etc., and tries to manage energy generation, transfers and

consumes and when necessary use the storage system or direct connection between production and consumption to create a balance between the amount and supply and demand of energy in that smart seaport, which results in increasing the efficiency and productivity of energy generation and transferring and reducing energy consumption and, by considering a significant amount of energy production in the world(71%) is still generated by fossil fuels[64], this reduction in fuel consumption will reduce the emission of pollutants and reduce the C.F.

In ports where renewable energies are also used as effective sources of energy production, the energy management system using smart energy networks increases the efficiency of balancing energy supply and demand, so if the amount of energy generated by renewable resources are more than the demand, the amount of excess generation will be stored for the subsequent consumption, which will result in more effective performance of the smart energy network infrastructures and then will require less hardware repairs and replacements, and consequently this issue will ultimately by the life cycle assessment C.F of the hardware production of networks will result less carbon emission, and then reduction of the C.F, and if the amount of energy produced by renewable sources in smart ports is less than the amount of energy demand, this shortage Energy production by fossil resources will be compensated and the use of smart energy management system along with smart energy network will reduce the amount of output by fossil resources and reduce the C.F in that port.

Acknowledgment

I want to express my deep gratitude to Professor Claudia Lizette Garay-Rondero from the School of Engineering and Sciences, Institute for the Future of Education Tecnologico de Monterrey, Mexico, and visiting Professor at Madrid Polytechnique University, Spain, for her patient guidance, enthusiastic encouragement, and valuable critiques in this research process.

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